

Learning styles and academic performance of nursing students in St. Dominic College of Asia

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Abstract

Some nursing students have different styles of learning that resulted in the outcome of their academic performance. The researchers determined the learning styles and academic performance of nursing students in St. Dominic College of Asia. Descriptive correlation type of research design was employed, a questionnaire, and the grades of level 2 nursing students from the registrar were used as sources of data. The tool was adopted from Fleming's VARK model to describe the learning styles of the respondents. Frequency and percentage distribution, and chi-square were used to statistically treat the data. Based on the data gathered, majority of the second year nursing students used kinesthetic type of learning which takes place by the student carrying out a physical activity, rather than listening to a lecture or watching a demonstration. It was followed by auditory a learning style, in which a person learns through listening. An auditory learner depends on learning and speaking as the main way of learning. While the 'read and write' learners preferred to read the instruction or book rather than watching it or listening to it. Lastly, visual learners are discussed where concepts, data and gathering information are associated with images and techniques. It is therefore concluded that kinesthetic style is the most preferred learning style of nursing students. There is also a very satisfactory academic performance among nursing students. There is a significant relationship between learning styles and academic performance of second year nursing students in St. Dominic College of Asia. It is therefore recommended that implementing effective teaching and learning activities that are suitable for students' learning styles will result in a good academic performance.

Keywords: *Learning styles; Academic performance; Nursing students; Learning experience; Acquisition of knowledge.*

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Introduction

Learning style refers to an individual's approach to acquiring knowledge to facilitate personal growth. Individuals possess varying learning styles through which they categorize, articulate, and recognize their acquisition of knowledge in many ways. In contemporary society, individuals have developed diverse learning methods, which they employ to facilitate rapid learning. Identifying the most efficient learning modes, such as visual, auditory, reading-writing, and kinesthetic, can be difficult. These are the four frequently employed strategies individuals frequently utilize to efficiently assimilate knowledge and digest information that aligns with their requirements. However, the most effective method for an individual to acquire knowledge always hinges on their ability to assimilate new concepts readily. Individuals possess distinct learning styles that are most effective and suitable for them. Regrettably, every learning style has benefits and drawbacks, making it challenging to determine the most effective approach to implement in the nursing field.

Individuals commonly use graphs and charts to comprehend information effectively through visual learning. Visual learners favored graphic elements over words because they needed images to comprehend and articulate concepts and ideas. On the other hand, auditory learners prefer to acquire knowledge through spoken content, such as lectures and discussions, because they process information by verbalizing their thoughts. The reading and writing learners are next in line, as they prefer receiving knowledge in written form. They enjoy reading and writing tasks because they effectively assimilate information through written language. Finally, kinesthetic learners are individuals who excel in learning through bodily activities. These learners prefer to develop specific plans based on their own direct experiences.

Understanding one's learning style enables individuals to optimize their learning experience. However, determining which of the four learning styles will most likely enhance academic success remains crucial. There were both benefits and drawbacks associated with the four (4) learning styles that had both advantages and disadvantages. Understanding an individual's preferred learning style can significantly enhance their ability to assimilate information and develop efficient strategies for learning. This knowledge is precious for nursing students striving to excel in their studies. Recent research has shown that providing students with access to knowledge in a format that they find comfortable can enhance their academic confidence. Assisting pupils in understanding and adapting to their learning styles or processes will enhance their confidence in comprehending knowledge. By doing so, students would have the capacity to engage in classroom discussions and actively apply their acquired knowledge to their clinical responsibilities.

Prospective students or learners are required to possess both critical and creative thinking skills. Several studies suggest that exposing students to different learning styles and utilizing diverse tactics, such as critical and creative thinking abilities, may enhance their ability to effectively engage in their academic and social environment, particularly when it comes to their responsibilities in a hospital setting. Utilizing these experiences in education might optimize an individual's capacity to develop into a discerning, innovative, and even productive thinker, which is considered essential for achieving outstanding academic results. Therefore, it is imperative that these aspiring nurses fully utilize the resources available to them in order to cater to their individual learning preferences as they begin their journey in college or university. Hence, it is advantageous for students to engage in activities that can optimize their learning and skill development in school. Students can enhance their information acquisition and achieve outstanding performance by utilizing their preferred learning methods (Jiraporncharoen et al., 2015).

Customizing learning tactics to accommodate unique learning styles is crucial to maximize a learner's potential. In this context, a recent study sought to pinpoint potential shifts in learners' learning styles following exposure to diverse learning styles in a "thinking skills course" during the first semester of their college or university programs. By discerning their learning strategies, individuals can enhance their understanding of the most efficient learning styles and procedures tailored to their specific needs. This understanding will unintentionally cause repercussions within the teaching-learning sphere. We can adjust teaching styles to accommodate the learners' needs at the early stages of their study instead of rigidly adhering to a specific teaching model. The absence of these insights led to a significant failure in recognizing and matching the learner's abilities to achieve outstanding academic success.

Recent research indicates that nursing students have distinct learning patterns (An, 2007; Hallin, 2014). Therefore, assessing nursing students' educational approaches would be advantageous to allow educators to develop an effective plan for practical and pragmatic instruction to ensure optimal learning and education. In addition, the influence of preferred learning styles on students' learning styles and study habits may also predict a nursing student's attitudes towards their demographic status and mental well-being. This applies both during the application process for nursing school and throughout their final year of study. Assessing the efficacy of learning styles may be critical in determining a student's individual characteristics and tailoring educational approaches, especially in the nursing profession.

On the contrary, universal learning procedures would improve the student's learning capacity, but it contradicts the premise that each student has unique learning experiences. Moreover, the methods or procedures with the most scientific evidence supporting their effectiveness require careful planning and substantial effort.

The primary objective of this study is to ascertain the notable correlation between learning styles and the academic achievement of nursing students. The aim is to determine the particular factors by which learning styles impact students' academic performance and assess the significance of learning styles in students' academic achievements. This study aims to recognize that nursing students can determine which learning styles are most beneficial in their courses. Furthermore, it is probable to determine an individual's learning style that is well-suited to them. This study aims to examine the most effective learning styles for processing knowledge, achieving outstanding academic success, and enhancing future nursing skills. Moreover, this study aims to examine whether the demographic characteristics of students, such as gender, age, and family status, influence their learning style. Additionally, it will explore how the various curricula experienced by nursing students impact their academic performance. The study aims to suggest a comprehensive program of activities for the nursing college to facilitate a deeper exploration of students' learning styles, thereby promoting improved academic achievement.

By recognizing that individuals have unique learning styles and employing tailored approaches or techniques, they can enhance their performance and effectively assimilate information beneficial to their achievements (Paiboonsithiwong et al., 2016). Consequently, the researchers aim to enhance teaching methods by focusing on successful strategies to provide a solid foundation for nursing students' learning. Furthermore, the researchers want to determine the most suitable learning styles for nursing students. It is essential to develop effective teaching methods that cater to varied learning styles to improve academic achievement. This study investigated individuals' learning styles to establish a solid foundation for improved academic performance during their tenure as nursing students. The creation of optimal learning environments consider various learning styles and environmental elements.

Methodology

This study determined the relationship between nursing students' learning styles and academic performance. The research design refers to the strategy prepared to integrate the various parts of the study coherently and logically, guaranteeing that the analysis problem may be adequately addressed. We conducted this study using an online survey for higher education students at St. Dominic College of Asia. This institution is located in Bacoor, Cavite, Region IV-A, Calabarzon. All the qualified nursing students from the second level, with a total of 34 participants in the study, voluntarily and willingly participated in this study. The participants were regular students with a single status, no children, and are enrolled this semester.

The questionnaire has two parts. The first part includes the cover letter that explains the purpose of the study and how to get the consent and cooperation of the respondents. Next is the respondent's profile, which includes the student's name, age, sex, family relationship, and religious affiliation. Respondents will respond to a series of questions about various learning styles by selecting from the bulleted choices. This will categorize each respondent's learning style as visual, auditory, reading and writing, and kinesthetic. The data gathered related to learning styles, and the researchers asked for the cooperation of the respondents to participate in the study. Frequency and percentage distribution were used to answer minor problem no.1 as to demographic profile. Mode was used to determine the dominant learning styles of the students, followed by frequency and percentage distribution, as well as for academic performance. Chi-Square was used to test the hypothesis on a significant relationship between learning styles and academic performance. 0.05 significance level was utilized as the point of reference for rejecting or accepting the hypothesis.

Results

Table 1. Profile Characteristics of the Respondents (n=34)

Profile	Measure	N	%
Sex	Male	4	11.76%
	Female	30	88.24%
Age	17 – 18	1	2.94%
	19 – 20	22	64.71%
	21 – 22	8	23.53%
	23 and above	3	8.82%
Family Relationship	Highly Favorable	13	38.24%
	Moderately Favorable	18	52.94%
	Not Favorable	3	8.82%
Religious Affiliation	Roman Catholic	26	76.47%
	Christian	3	8.82%
	Agnostic	2	5.88%
	Born Again	1	2.94%
	Protestant	1	2.94%
	UMC (United Methodist Church)	1	2.94%

Table 1 presents the profile characteristics of the respondents. Female students numbered most among the second year level with 30 (88.24%) and male students with 4 (11.76%). As to Age over 34 respondents, 22 respondents (64.71%) were at the age of 19-20 years old, eight (8) respondents (23.53%) were at the age 21-22, three (3) (8.83%) were at the age of 23 years old and above. Lastly, only one (2.94%) was aged 17-18 years old. Regarding the Family Relationship, 18 (52.94%) students were Moderately Favorable in their relationship with their family or relatives, and 13 (38.24%) were Highly Favorable in their family or relatives' relationships. Lastly, 3 (8.82%) of the remaining students were not favorable in their family relationships. In Religious Affiliation, over 34 respondents, 26 (76.47%) were Roman Catholics, 3 (8.82%) were Christians, Agnostic with a frequency of 2 (5.88%), Born Again with 1 (2.94%), Protestant with a frequency of 1 (2.94%), and UMC or United Methodist Church with 1 (2.94%).

Table 2. Learning Styles of the Respondents (n=34)

Learning Styles	Frequency	Percentage
Visual	4	12%
Auditory	12	35%
Reading-Writing	3	8%
Kinesthetic	15	45%

Table 2 presents the dominant learning styles of the student participants. It shows the highest score or is most frequently checked by the respondents. From the 16 questions, Kinesthetic obtained the highest frequency of 15 (45%), and the lowest is Visual with 4 (12%), while Auditory with 12 (35%), and Reading-Writing with 3 (8%)

Table 3. Academic Performance of the Respondents

Academic Performance Distribution	Frequency	Percentage
Good	4	11.76
Very Satisfactory	10	29.41
Satisfactory	7	20.58
Average	5	14.70
Fair	5	14.70
Passed	1	2.94
Failed	2	5.88

Table 3 presents the frequency and the percentage of the grades when interpreted in academic performance. The findings showed that respondents have good ratings with 11.76% (n=4), very satisfactory has 29.41% (n=10), satisfactory has 20.58% (n=7), average has 14.70% (n=5), fair has 14.70% (n=5), passed has 2.94% (n=1), and failed has 5.88% (n=2).

Table 4. Learning Styles of the Respondents (n=34)

Learning Styles	Academic Performance	Interpretation
Visual	82.54%	Average
Auditory	83.81%	Satisfactory
Reading-Writing	82.08%	Average
Kinesthetic	83.93%	Satisfactory

Table 4 presents the relationship between learning styles and academic performance and its interpretation. Visual has an Average result of 82.54% when it comes to academic grades. Auditory has a Satisfactory result of 83.81% when it comes to academic grades. Reading-Writing has an Average result of 82.08% when it comes to academic grades. Lastly, Kinesthetic has a Satisfactory result of 83.93% when it comes to academic grades.

Table 5. Relationship between learning styles and academic performance of the respondents

Learning Styles	Average		Satisfactory		Chi-Square	Sig.
	f	%	f	%		
Visual	9	26.47	2	5.88	7.815	0.004
Auditory	5	14.71	7	20.59		
Reading-Writing	1	2.94	2	5.88		
Kinesthetic	5	14.71	10	29.41		

Table 5 presents the relationship between the learning styles of academic performance [$\chi^2 = (3) = 7.815$ $p < 0.004$]. This means that statistically, there is a significant relationship between the participants' grades and learning styles. Since the p-value is 0.004, which is, in fact, less than 0.05 level of significance, we reject the null hypothesis with the results across the learning styles and academic performance or grades of the participants.

Discussion

The results revealed that kinesthetic learning has the highest learning style, with 45% (n=15) of students. This means that the kinesthetic learning style is the most dominant among the four categories. The Auditory learning style follows this with 35% (n=12), and only 8% (n=3) have a Reading-Writing learning style among the participants. The probable reason the kinesthetic learning style is the most dominant learning style among the 4 categories is that kinesthetic learning enhances analytical skills. In contrast to auditory and reading-writing learning methods, which simply give information, kinesthetic learning methods enable people to find knowledge independently. Kinesthetic learning involves physical interaction between the students and the environment (Begel et al., 2004; Molsbee, 2011). Kinesthetic activities are primarily performed outdoors, where students can explore the environment. A teacher who teaches kinesthetic activities should be aware of the appropriateness of the said activity that will be performed. Physical education is an example of a subject where a kinesthetic learner learns more. Active learning or kinesthetic learning approach is a solution for those who have difficulty paying attention for a long time because students expect to be physically and mentally involved during the lecture.

The active learning process is where a student applies what he or she has learned. A nursing student's approaches to and satisfaction with work, stress, and mental health, both when applying to nursing school and during their final year, may also be predicted by how their preferred learning styles affect their study habits and learning styles. The power of an auditory learner lies in their ability to perceive and then remember what they have learned. An auditory learner can learn through listening to different sounds. In a typical classroom situation, a student can learn without looking at the instructor's visual presentation. This suggests that teaching styles in the classroom, like presentations or debates, play to the power of the auditory learner. Opponents of auditory learning claim that this strategy often has distractions that can impair learning. Audible audio materials available on the internet, such as auditory learning opponents, said the learning environment differs notably in classrooms; this helps communicate with this kind of learner more efficiently (Mahmoud et al., 2019). When students read and then write down what they have read on paper or a board, they learn more effectively under the reading-writing category. Dictionaries, including the Internet, PowerPoint, written responses, and language signs, are preferred tools. Reading is one of the significant practices that have a great advantage in raising students' writing abilities. When students love to read, they usually construct sentences with the same level of words they encountered while reading (Molsbee, 2011).

The ability of a student to fulfill the aims, accomplishments, and objectives of the course or program is referred to as academic performance. These are represented by grades, which are the results of an assessment that includes passing or failing specific exams, courses, or subjects. According to Li et al. (2014), academic performance is the knowledge that students and teachers have learned and/or the learning objectives they have set for themselves over a predetermined period of time, as measured by grades. It depends on academic interaction, which is dependent on home environment and study habits. This ensured that every student could assess their academic performance based on their home environment, learning abilities, academic background, study habits, and home environment. The student's personality characteristics, personal ambitions, motivation, teacher encouragement, and the teacher's level of experience have a significant impact on student academic performance (Li et al., 2014).

The results revealed that the kinesthetic learning style has an 83.93%. It is also a satisfactory grade when it is interpreted as academic performance. Some teachers may perceive their behavior as distracted or bored, while students refer to it as "fidgety." Also, kinesthetic learners had excellent hand-eye coordination through rapid responses, outstanding muscle memory (can repeat it once after doing it), outstanding experimenters, good at sports, well-performing in art and theatre, and high energy levels (Bangcola, 2016). According to their tendency toward movement, getting information from written materials or listening is not as easy as the abovementioned methods. They typically have trouble sitting still and paying attention, so it can be challenging at times. They may require frequent breaks while studying and frequently struggle in classes that require a lot of reading and lectures (Lai et al., 2015).

In addition, the auditory learning style is 83.81%. Auditory learners have a satisfactory grade when it is interpreted in terms of academic performance. Auditory learners must recall what they hear when they absorb information through auditory representation. Podcasts and radio broadcasting are examples of how an auditory learner learns the most. For such learners, auditory components such as sound, pitch, and loudness are all essential (Kayalar & Kayalar, 2017). However, auditory learners may have difficulty reading and writing assignments, but they can move their mouths too and read aloud. That is what auditory learners sometimes refer to themselves as. Auditory learners enjoy talking and watching others speak to understand, but they may have difficulty reading quietly or remaining engaged in a quiet classroom (Mahmoud et al., 2019).

Furthermore, the visual learning style is 82.54%, and when it is interpreted in terms of academic performance, it shows an average grade. Visual learning can be characterized as the assimilation of visually formatted content. In the classroom, learners better understand knowledge when they see it (Aisami, 2015). Visual content is present in different ways, such as photographs, flowcharts, diagrams, videos, animations, graphs, cartoons, coloring books, slideshows or PowerPoint decks, posters, films, games, and flashcards.

Additionally, Kelly and Banzhaf (2020) claim that instructors who use an overhead projector or whiteboard to display the main points of a lesson or who provide an outline to follow during the lecture are beneficial to students who are visual learners. These particular students prefer to study alone in a quiet room and frequently gain from the information found in textbooks and class notes; this is how they were able to improve their academic performance. Visual learners frequently interpret details through the “mind’s eye” (one’s ability to see things through the mind) when attempting to recall something. They tend to memorize the complete or most details of a particular scenario.

The reading-writing learning style has 82.08%. They have an average grade when interpreted in terms of academic performance. Reading is one of the significant practices that have greatly increased students’ writing abilities. When students love to read, they usually construct sentences with the same level of words that they encounter whenever they are reading. With each grade, academic standards increase, and the reading task becomes even more critical. Experts believe reading is a fundamental ability that influences every aspect of a child’s academic performance and is a crucial component of life. The study also shows a strong correlation between the academic achievement of the participants and their learning styles. According to Dalmolin et al. (2018), learning styles and students’ academic achievement were positively correlated.

Conclusion

This study examined the different learning styles and explored how they impact academic performance among St. Dominic College of Asia nursing students. Nursing students can unlock their full potential and excel in their studies by understanding the connection between learning styles and academic success. The learning style of nursing students can have a significant impact on their academic performance. When students align their study techniques with their preferred learning style, they can maximize their understanding and retention of information. By utilizing study techniques that cater to their learning style, nursing students can enhance their comprehension and retention of complex nursing concepts. This leads to better performance in exams and assignments. Understanding one’s learning style allows nursing students to develop personalized study strategies that are efficient and effective for them. This saves time and energy by focusing on techniques most beneficial to their learning style. Nursing students are more engaged and motivated when they study in a way that aligns with their learning style. This enthusiasm translates into increased focus and dedication to their studies, improving academic performance.

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